

IMPACT OF SMOOTHING TIME CONSTANTS ON GAST-E OBSERVABLES DURING SCINTILLATION EVENTS

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ABSTRACT – This paper evaluates the performance of smoothing filters applied to observables used in GAST-E under ionospheric scintillation conditions. Additionally, it provides a brief overview of the current state of GBAS research and development in Brazil. Motivated by INCT GNSS NavAer interest in enhancing GNSS reliability within Brazilian airspace—and building upon national research efforts—this study investigates the behavior of smoothing filter time constants in the presence of equatorial plasma bubbles (EPBs), leading to scintillation occurrences. Data from one station of a network of monitoring stations in São José dos Campos, SP, are analyzed to assess how different time constants affect observables during ionospheric disturbances. Results indicate that longer time-constant filters effectively reduce noise during quiescent periods; however, their convergence is significantly challenged by frequent cycle slips during intense scintillation, thereby compromising their reliability for positioning solutions. These insights aim to contribute to the development of robust smoothing standards for GAST-E operations in challenging equatorial regions.

RESUMO – Este trabalho avalia o desempenho de filtros de suavização aplicados nas observáveis utilizados no GAST-E sob condições de cintilação ionosférica. Além disso, apresenta uma breve visão geral do estado atual da pesquisa e desenvolvimento do GBAS no Brasil. Motivado pelo interesse do INCT GNSS NavAer em aumentar a confiabilidade do GNSS no espaço aéreo brasileiro - e com base nos esforços de pesquisa nacionais - este estudo investiga o comportamento das constantes de tempo do filtro de suavização na presença de bolhas de plasma equatorial (EPBs), levando a ocorrências de cintilação. Dados de uma estação de uma rede de estações de monitoramento em São José dos Campos, SP, são analisados para avaliar como diferentes constantes de tempo afetam as observáveis durante distúrbios ionosféricos. Os resultados indicam que filtros com constantes de tempo mais longas reduzem efetivamente o ruído durante períodos intensos de cintilação ionosférica; no entanto, sua convergência é significativamente desafiada por frequentes perdas de ciclo durante a forte cintilação, comprometendo assim sua confiabilidade para soluções de posicionamento. Estes conhecimentos visam contribuir para o desenvolvimento de normas de suavização robustas para operações GAST-E em regiões equatoriais difíceis.

1 INTRODUCTION

The implementation of Ground-Based Augmentation System Dual-Frequency Multi-Constellation (GBAS DFMC) services holds significant potential for extending the operational use of GBAS to low-latitude regions such as Brazil. In these regions, the real-time use of Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) faces unique challenges; ionospheric effects frequently affect signal integrity, potentially causing cycle slips, loss of lock, and signal interruptions. Such disturbances can undermine the reliability and performance of GBAS, adversely impacting precision approach capabilities in civil aviation.

GBAS is a GNSS-based augmentation system that supports precision approach and landing by providing real-time differential corrections from ground stations located at airports. Operating under standards like GAST-C and GAST-D, current GBAS implementations use L1 frequency signals—primarily from GPS—and apply smoothing algorithms such as the Hatch filter to enhance positioning accuracy and integrity. The Hatch filter is a recursive linear combination of code and carrier measurements, designed to mitigate multipath errors and other unmodeled receiver effects (noise). Its formulation is presented in Hatch (1983) and Pullen (2017). The filter operation starts at the first data epoch, with an initial unitary value that progressively increases until reaching the chosen filter constant. From that point, the filter parameter remains constantly fixed. In the event of a cycle slip, the filter is reset, as described in RTCA DO-253C (2008). However, in low-latitude regions like Brazil, intense ionospheric activity can trigger signal fluctuations and cycle slips, reducing system performance and reliability. These limitations underscore the need for more resilient GBAS architectures capable of operating with multiple frequencies and constellations (PULLEN, 2017; RTCA DO-253C, 2008).

To address these challenges, the architecture currently under development for GBAS DFMC – referred to as GAST-E (MURPHY et al., 2023) – prioritizes GNSS observations based on the Divergence-Free (DFree) linear combination. This approach offers the advantage of minimizing the code-carrier divergence (CCD) effect through a simplified pseudorange smoothing process. One of the main innovations in GAST-E is the adoption of an extended smoothing time constant of 600 seconds, significantly longer than those utilized in earlier standards (100 seconds for GAST-C, and 30 or 100 seconds for GAST-D). The rationale for this longer time constant is to further suppress noisy code-derived measurements, thereby improving system integrity. GAST-E also provides the option of fallback to Ionospheric-Free (IFree) smoothing and conventional single-frequency GAST-C/D processing in case DFree smoothing becomes impractical.

It is important to note that the definition of a fixed smoothing time constant for GAST-E remains under active discussion. There is potential for GAST-E to implement a large or variable smoothing time constant, or possibly no fixed value at all. In this approach, satellites may contribute to the position solution even during the transient phase of their smoothing filters, resulting in satellites being used at different states of smoothing within the same epoch. This flexibility is particularly relevant for equatorial regions, where frequent signal loss due to scintillation can limit filter convergence and system availability. In such a framework, all relevant error models must be properly scaled to account for increased noise and multipath from partially smoothed satellites. While research and validation are ongoing and no final decision has been made, understanding how ionospheric scintillation impacts various smoothing time constants is fundamental to the evolution of GAST-E and is a central focus of this paper.

Given these ongoing developments and the unique GNSS challenges faced in Brazil, national efforts have been directed toward advancing research and operational understanding in this domain. Brazil's main Air Navigation Service Provider (ANSP) and regulatory authority, the Department of Airspace Control (DECEA), has been actively engaged in research on GNSS augmentation systems at low latitudes since the early 2010s. Motivated by the earlier attempt to certify a GBAS CAT-I station at Rio de Janeiro International Airport (SBGL) (MARINI-PEREIRA et al., 2021), the Institute of Airspace Control (ICEA)—a technical arm of DECEA—undertook comprehensive investigations into the impacts of severe ionospheric activity on GBAS, SBAS, and ABAS. Although these efforts led to a temporary pause in the pursuit of System Design and Operation Approvals, they reinforced the importance of ongoing research in this area.

Established in 2017 under Brazil's National Institute for Science and Technology (INCT) funding model and supported by the Brazilian National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq), São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP) and the Secretary of Civil Aviation (SAC), this group has driven both innovative research and the development of GNSS expertise among students and professionals (MONICO et al., 2022). Noteworthy achievements include the deployment of a network comprising over 40 GNSS receivers with scintillation monitoring capabilities distributed throughout the Brazilian territory (PAULA et al., 2023). Several investigations have been carried out so far. At this contribution, the aim is to analyze the performance of different pseudorange smoothing time constants proposed for GAST-E when subjected to ionospheric scintillation, with a focus on results derived from the ICEA monitoring station (Figure 1). This work contributes to assessing the operational viability of advanced GBAS MFMC services in challenging low-latitude environments.

2 METODOLOGY

The INCT group recently deployed in São Jose dos Campos - SP, a set of monitoring stations specifically designed to collect GNSS data for GAST-E experiments and simulations. As shown in Figure 1, the three eastern stations (ICEA, SJCE, and INPE) simulate the GBAS ground reference function, while the two stations to the west (SJCU and IACT) represent approaching aircraft on differing azimuths, although they remain stationary for data gathering. All stations are equipped with Septentrio PolaRx5S receivers and choke ring antennas. Data collection with a sample rate of 1s (1 Hz) started in November 2024 and remains ongoing. A similar monitoring configuration was previously implemented at UNESP University in Presidente Prudente to assess smoothing time constants under local ionospheric conditions (SOUZA et al., 2025; SILVA et al., 2023).

Figure 1 – Setup of ground stations in São José dos Campos to simulate the Aircraft/GBAS configuration.

Source: Authors (2025).

To reach the aim of this contribution, a smoothing analysis was carried out for the ICEA station using the Hatch filter for the following observable combinations: single frequency L1, DFree L1 and L5, and IFree. Smoothing time constants of 0 (raw measurement), 30, 100, and 600 seconds were applied to all these combinations. Data from GPS and Galileo satellites were used, specifically from the L1/E1 and L5/E5a frequencies. The ICEA station analyzed data from DOYs 031 and 032/2025 (January 31st and February 1st, respectively). For all data presented, an elevation mask of 10° was applied to mitigate interferences—other than scintillation—at low elevation angles.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 2 shows the ionospheric amplitude scintillation index (S_4) for these days at the ICEA station. GPS satellites are represented in blue, while Galileo satellites are shown in red. Scintillation activity is noteworthy around or after 0:00 UTC (9:00 pm local time) on both days, with S_4 values exceeding 1.2 for some satellites, indicating strong irregularities derived from Equatorial Plasma Bubbles (EPB).

Figure 3 shows the S_4 index for GPS PRN 11 (G11) from around 0:00 to 5:00 LT. During this period, the most intense activity occurs approximately between 23:30 and 01:00 LT, with S_4 values indicating the presence of EPBs (Equatorial Plasma Bubbles).

The intense scintillation period is reflected in the L1 pseudorange smoothing, presented in the panels of Figure 4 for three different time constants. Due to the magnitude of the pseudorange measurements, the values were subtracted by the carrier-phase observable at the same frequency, enabling the analysis of small- to medium-scale variabilities. This approach is adopted by all measurements presented herein.

Figure 2 – S_4 scintillation index for ICEA station between Jan. 31st and Feb. 1st, for an elevation mask of 10°.

Figure 3 – S₄ index for G11.

Figure 4 – Carrier-smoothed L1 pseudorange for G11 with different time constants. Resetting measurements of the filter for each time are shown before convergence.

Figure 4 also depicts the resulting smoothing before the convergence time, following filter resets due to loss of lock, about 9 resetting's. As expected, it is evident that longer time constants require longer periods to recover after frequent cycle slips, even when these slips occur during periods of low scintillation, such as between 01:00 and 02:00 LT.

The effects of EPBs on the DFree smoothing of L1 observables can be seen in Figure 5 for different time constants, along with the unsmoothed measurement (0 s). Only measurements after the convergence period are shown. The smoothing effect for the 600 s filter is clear during periods without scintillation. However, the filter with this time constant cannot converge for approximately 40 minutes (between 23:40 and 00:20 LT) during the scintillation period.

Similar effects are seen for the DFree smoothing on L5 in Figure 6. Two different aspects are clearly identified in this case. First, the unsmoothed measurements (0 s) are significantly less noisy than those at the L1 frequency. Second, longer time constants respond more slowly to sudden or minor variations in this frequency, which is more evident for the 600 s filter, even during periods of low scintillation.

Effects of EPBs on the smoothing of the Ionospheric-Free combination for G11 are shown in Figure 7 for different time constants, along with the unsmoothed measurement (0 s). As explained earlier, the same strategy of subtracting the carrier-phase measurement from the observable combination was applied. In this respect, compared to the DFree combination, the range of values is lower, as expected due to the characteristics of the IF combination. The smoothing effect is clear, increasing with time constant. The 600 s filter appears to respond appropriately to sudden variations in the IF during the periods it is available. Nevertheless, the same issue is noted during the strong scintillation period: the 600 s filter cannot converge, and therefore is not available, during the continuous 40 minutes the satellite is under strong scintillation.

Figure 5 – Divergence-Free (L1) for G11 with smoothing constants 0 (raw), 30, 100, 600 seconds.

Figure 6 – Divergence-Free (L5) for G11 with smoothing constants 0 (raw), 30, 100, 600 seconds.

Figure 7 – Ionospheric-Free (IF) for G11 with smoothing constants 0 (raw), 30, 100, 600 seconds.

The same analysis was performed for other Galileo satellites that were also affected by scintillation and presented similar results to those shown for G11. Figure 8 presents the S_4 scintillation index for the Galileo E06 satellite. Moderate scintillation activity ($S_4 > 0.5$) is noted around 9 pm, which intensifies to stronger levels ($S_4 \sim 1.0$) around 10 pm. After local midnight, scintillation further intensifies, with the S_4 index exceeding 1.0.

Figure 8 – S_4 index for E06.

The scintillation effect is observed in the DFree combination for E1 on satellite E06, as shown in Figure 9. Around 9 pm, when scintillation levels begin to increase, the 600 s smoothing filter is interrupted due to several cycle slips, causing the 30 s filter to reset and recover multiple times. The 100 s filter struggles to recover and can converge only after the S_4 drops below 0.5. As scintillation activity increases, several cycle slips occur, and the receiver loses lock with this satellite for approximately 30 minutes. After that, the filters with 30 s and 100 s time constants can recover but still experience cycle slips. When scintillation activity decreases around 11 pm, the filters recover but lose lock for a few minutes due to site obstructions. Right after midnight, as the satellite is descending, strong scintillation activity occurs, and a large jump is observed in the DFree, with several cycle slips and a complete absence of results from the 600 s filter.

Figure 9 – Divergence-Free (L1) for E06 with smoothing constants 0 (raw), 30, 100, 600 seconds.

For the application of the DFree combination on E5, the overall behavior during scintillation is quite similar to the effects observed using the E1 frequency, as shown in Figure 10. The most prominent aspect is the lower noise in the raw measurements and the offset effect observed with the 600 s filter compared to the other time constants. This effect is particularly noticeable during minor or sudden variations.

Figure 11 presents the application of the smoothing filter with all mentioned time constants on the IFree combination. The smoothing effect is clear, with the 600 s filter performing well in response to sudden or minor variations. However, the issue with this longer time constant filter remains the extended time required to converge after frequent cycle slips or loss of lock due to scintillation.

Figure 10 – Divergence-Free (E5) for E06 with smoothing constants 0 (raw), 30, 100, 600 seconds.

Figure 11 – Ionospheric-Free (IFree) for E06 with smoothing constants 0 (raw), 30, 100, 600 seconds.

One last case is presented for the same night, this time for the Galileo E09 satellite. Figure 12 shows the S_4 index for this satellite during the period between 18:00 LT on January 31st and 02:00 LT on February 1st. Moderate scintillation is observed around 9 pm and 10:45 pm. After 11 pm, scintillation levels increase and reach stronger values around local midnight.

Figure 12 – S_4 index for E09.

Analyzing only the IFree combination, a minor variation is observed after 9 pm, during the period of moderate scintillation. Due to a cycle slip, all filters must reset, and, given the moderate scintillation, they each take exactly the time of their respective constants to recover, without additional interruption. Around 10:45 pm, similar behavior is observed at the same scintillation intensity ($S_4 \sim 0.5$).

After 11 pm, scintillation activity increases significantly, and several cycle slips occur. As a result, the 30 s and 100 s smoothing filters reset multiple times up to the first minutes after midnight, when a sudden jump is observed in the IFree combination. After attempting to reset around 11:15 pm, the 600 s filter can converge only around 00:30, following the sudden variation, when scintillation briefly decreases before increasing again after 20 minutes, causing several more cycle slips and filter resets. With the satellite descending at a low elevation angle under strong scintillation, the 600 s filter is unable to reset before the satellite drops below the 10° elevation mask.

Figure 13 – Ionospheric-Free (IFree) for E09 with smoothing constants 0 (raw), 30, 100, 600 seconds.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the impact of ionospheric scintillation on combinations of observations required for GAST-E, with a focus on the effectiveness of different smoothing filters and time constants applied to DFree and IFree combinations.

Results across the analyzed satellites in both frequencies (L1/E1 and L5/E5a) consistently demonstrated that while longer time constant filters, such as the 600 s filter, offer superior noise reduction and effectively smooth data during quiet ionospheric conditions, their ability to converge is significantly degraded during periods of intense scintillation. Frequent cycle slips and loss of lock, particularly under strong scintillation pose substantial challenges to filter performance, often delaying recovery or preventing convergence entirely. Additionally, raw measurements on the L5/E5a frequency exhibited less noise compared to L1 and E1, though similar difficulties with filter recovery were observed during scintillation events.

Overall, the findings underscore the complex interplay between filter time constants and scintillation activity. They highlight the need for adaptive filtering strategies capable of maintaining robust performance even under challenging weather conditions. Possible approaches include the adoption of variable or flexible smoothing constants, allowing the system to dynamically adjust the time constant according to ionospheric conditions, as well as strategies that dynamically integrate multiple observable combinations according to ionospheric patterns. These insights are intended to contribute to the ongoing discussion regarding the establishment of standards for smoothing techniques in low-latitude environments, which are subject to strong influences from EPBs and scintillation.

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